

Compressive Properties of Pyramid Lattice with Various Non-uniform Cross-section

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Abstract: Lightweight sandwich structure is highly attractive in aerospace and aeronautic engineering due to its high specific strength and stiffness, evidently vibration and noise reduction or heat dissipation functions. As typical examples, honeycomb and foam structures have been successfully applied in spacecraft and aeroplane design, which drives further research on new cellular material cores. Lattice truss materials proposed in 2000s have been proved the further advantages of lightweight and multi-function compared to traditional sandwich materials, and therefore currently considered the most promising lightweight materials. Over the last decade, many scholars have carried out extensive research on the lattice material configuration, including various lattice types such as tetrahedron^[1], pyramid^[2], octahedron^[3], X-type^[4] and gyroid^[5] and hollow^[6] or hierarchical^[7] design scheme. In recent years, the additive manufacturing methods are developing rapidly and especially applicable to three-dimensional lattice material with internal complex configuration^[8], which makes it possible to manufacture lattice material with variable cross-section. Although some correlational studies have been proposed about truss with variable cross-section^[9, 10], they are lack of comprehensiveness including stiffness, strength and stability, and has not been applied to lattice materials.

In this paper, the mechanical properties of single truss is first deduced. The longitudinal cross-section is assumed to be constant, hyperbolic or elliptic form:

$$\begin{cases} y = r & \text{constant cross-section} \\ \frac{y^2}{m} - \frac{x^2}{n} = 1 & \text{hyperbolic cross-section} \\ \frac{y^2}{m} + \frac{x^2}{n} = 1 & \text{elliptic cross-section} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The stiffness of truss is calculated analytically using integration of axial strain, and the buckling eigenvalue is deduced explicitly through introducing parameter variation in equilibrium equation, that is:

$$E = \begin{cases} E_0 & \text{constant cross-section} \\ \frac{(3 + \xi^2) \cdot \text{atan}(\xi) \cdot E_0}{3\xi} & \text{hyperbolic cross-section} \\ \frac{(3 - \xi^2) \cdot \text{atanh}(\xi) \cdot E_0}{3\xi} & \text{elliptic cross-section} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$\lambda = \begin{cases} \lambda_0 & \text{constant cross-section} \\ \frac{9\xi^2 [\pi^2 - 4\text{atan}^2(\xi)] \cdot \lambda_0}{\pi^2 [(3 + \xi^2) \text{atan}(\xi)]^2} & \text{hyperbolic cross-section} \\ \frac{9\xi^2 [\pi^2 + 4\text{atanh}^2(\xi)] \cdot \lambda_0}{\pi^2 [(3 - \xi^2) \text{atanh}(\xi)]^2} & \text{elliptic cross-section} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Fig.1 Comparison of mechanical properties for uniform cross-section and elliptic cross-section

The closed form solution shows that the mechanical property of truss with hyperbolic cross-section is worse than that with equal cross-section, and the truss with elliptical cross-section may be better. Subsequently, the elliptic cross-section is applied in the practical pyramid lattice, and its advantages and disadvantages in stiffness, strength and stability are discussed in detail compared with traditional pyramid lattice.

Fig.2 Effective compressive strength for various relative density and elliptic cross-section

Fig.3 Relationship of effective stress and strain for pyramid lattice

Finite element methods are adopted to confirm the accuracy of closed form solutions. Numerical example includes pyramid lattice with elliptical and equal cross-section. Both eigenvalue buckling and arc length method are applied, and the first order buckling mode is introduced as geometric imperfections in the latter method. Numerical results show that the stiffness of pyramid lattice with elliptic cross-section is only 16.4% weaker than that with equal cross-section. In terms of stability capacity, both eigenvalue buckling method and arc length method are in good agreement with abovementioned analytical solution. Moreover, it is proved that lattice with elliptical cross-section is higher than that with equal cross-section, and the difference is between 30.4% and 31.8% in all the methods. Both finite element methods show the same failure modes as spiral bending, but the instability position predicted by arc length method is closer to the end of truss. In addition, compressive strength is reduced with increasing of defects in trusses. In short, elliptic cross-section in longitudinal direction can obviously improve equivalent compressive strength in condition that the stiffness is decreased slightly for pyramid lattice with low relative density.

Keywords: Lattice; Compressive strength; Elliptic cross-section; Stiffness; Stability

Conclusion: Combining with currently feasible additive manufacturing process, a new variable cross-section design method is innovatively proposed. Under the same volume, mechanical properties of pyramid lattices with equal cross-section and variable cross-section are compared by both theoretical and numerical methods, and the following conclusions are obtained:

- (1) The stiffness of lattice with equal cross-section is the highest;
- (2) Only focusing on compressive strength, the lattice with equal cross-section is the most appropriate;
- (3) Considering both compressive strength and stability, the elliptic cross-section pyramid lattice is preferred for relative density lower than 0.03, and its carrying capacity can be increased by 31% over that with equal cross-section for the parameter ξ is 0.906. This research result has high engineering value because the pyramid lattice with much lower relative density possesses obvious lightweight advantages and can be manufactured much easily.

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